

Polypropylene-Reinforced Cement Sheeting for Use as Roofing and Cladding Elements

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ABSTRACT

The development of a composite in which cement is reinforced by continuous opened networks of fibrillated polypropylene film has particular application as an alternative to asbestos-cement for use as sheeting elements for roofing and cladding.

In the paper fundamental research conducted at the University of Surrey is related to parameters which are important for an effective material for corrugated sheeting. The tensile stress-strain curve and flexural load-deflection curve, the achievement of closely spaced, virtually invisible cracks and the impact strength of the composite are discussed in relation to fibre volume content, fibre modulus of elasticity and fibre characteristics affecting bond between matrix and fibre. The load-deflection relationship of a typical polypropylene-reinforced cement corrugated sheet is compared to that of an asbestos-cement sheet of similar profile and is discussed with reference to performance standards for fibre-reinforced cement sheeting.

INTRODUCTION

There has been considerable activity in recent years in the development of new composite materials suitable for use in flat or corrugated sheet form as alternatives to asbestos-cement (1). Although asbestos-cement has a number of technical limitations as a sheeting material, in particular its brittleness and poor impact resistance, it is unlikely that alternative materials could win a major share of its market (while asbestos fibres are in cheap supply) were it not for the increased awareness of the health hazards arising from asbestos-based materials. Sweden banned the manufacture of asbestos-cement in 1976, and elsewhere in Scandinavia, Western Europe and the USA, the replacement of asbestos-cement is taking place. The size of the market is considerable, with an annual production of approximately 30 million tonnes of asbestos-cement.

An alternative material in which the cement matrix is reinforced by continuous opened networks of fibrillated polypropylene film was developed at the University of Surrey in 1976 (2,3). The use of continuous fibrillated networks, as shown in Figure 1, allows a sufficient fibre volume fraction to be incorporated in thin sheets to ensure fine multiple cracking and produces a

quasi-ductile, impact resistant material of great potential. The particular end application considered in this paper is its use, in corrugated form, as a roofing and cladding element for buildings. Commercial development of the material is well advanced, with test marketing due to commence shortly.

IMPORTANT PROPERTIES FOR A CEMENT-BASED SHEETING MATERIAL

Before discussing specific material properties of a polypropylene-reinforced composite and the parameters on which the properties depend, some general requirements of a cement-based sheeting material are considered.

(i) In normal use, the sheeting will operate in the uncracked state. The fibre reinforcement essentially provides a reserve of strength to maintain the integrity of the unit under overload conditions, impact, misuse or under adverse conditions which are difficult to quantify for design purposes e.g. stresses induced by restrained shrinkage or thermal movements or by fixings. While the ultimate strength and strain capacity are, therefore, important (particularly if toughness is to be achieved) the stress at which significant cracking becomes apparent is likely to determine section sizes necessary to withstand design service loads. This stress should be as high as possible consistent with an economic material.

(ii) However, should matrix cracking occur, cracks should be as fine as possible and virtually invisible to the naked eye. This not only avoids concern about material appearance, but it should also prevent the penetration of moisture through cracks in sufficient quantity to allow droplets to form on the underside of sheeting. Furthermore fine cracks are likely to seal themselves quickly as fresh hydration products form from previously unhydrated cement.

(iii) If a quasi-ductile composite is considered serviceable in the cracked condition under normal loads, then in specifying acceptable performance criteria, deflection limitations may become important (for a brittle composite, failure occurs before deflection becomes critical). Thus there may be benefits in the composite which exhibits a relatively stiff post-crack region and, hence, in the normal flexural situation, can sustain loads at reduced deflections.

(iv) A high impact strength is desirable and is essentially dependent on the volume fraction, strength and strain to failure of the reinforcement.

(v) A sheeting material should be durable over the lifetime of a building which is likely to be in excess of 25 years.

PROPERTIES OF POLYPROPYLENE-REINFORCED CEMENT

Tensile Stress-strain and Flexural Load-deflection Relationships

The theoretical stress-strain relationship developed by Aveston et al (4,5) for a brittle matrix reinforced by aligned continuous, linear elastic fibres is broadly applicable to the polypropylene-reinforced cement composite under discussion, as shown by the typical stress-strain relationship of Figure 2 for a composite comprising of 7% by volume of opened film networks. The initial stiff uncracked portion of the curve, essentially controlled by matrix properties, is followed by a region of increasing strain at approximately constant stress whilst multiple cracking occurs. Upon completion of cracking, increasing composite strain results in further extension of the fibres until fibre failure occurs, the modulus of elasticity here being determined by the fibre modulus and fibre volume fraction. The flexural load-deflection relationship is stiff and essentially linear up to a load equivalent to a bending stress of about 10-12 MN/m² (calculated assuming elastic stress blocks with the neutral axis at mid depth). Thereafter, the deflection of the cracked composite increases more rapidly under increasing load. The point at which the tensile or flexural curve departs from the stiff linear region is hereafter called the Bend Over Point (BOP).

It has been found that the BOP in tension can be increased in two practical ways, (i) by increasing the fibre volume fraction or (ii) by increasing the fibre modulus (Figure 3) (6).

Brittle matrix composites fail in a more complex manner than the matrix alone. Extra energy-absorbing mechanisms such as fibre debonding, increased fibre strain energy, fibre/matrix friction and plastic deformation of angled fibres may increase the work of fracture of the composite. Further, the crack may be blunted by pores at the fibre/matrix interface or may be deviated into a non-critical path by the debonding of the interface ahead of the crack tip (if the interface is weak). Should the crack opening be restricted to less than 2 microns by increased fibre volume fraction or increased fibre modulus, the crack itself remains load bearing, hence altering the release of strain energy from the matrix.

Increasing the fibre volume fraction or the fibre modulus also reduces the strain at which multiple cracking is completed (Figure 3) and obviously increases the stiffness exhibited after cracking is complete. The attendant beneficial effect on flexural performance is illustrated in Figure 4, in which an increased BOP achieved by a higher fibre modulus is also apparent.

There is some reduction in strain to failure in using a fibre with a high modulus, but within the range of practicable polypropylene or polyethylene fibres, the reduction is not critical to composite performance.

At the present time, it is unlikely that the extra cost of introducing a high fibre volume fraction or high modulus fibre reinforcement will be off-set by the reduced section size required due to a higher BOP.

Crack Spacing

The achievement of very fine cracks implies that the final crack spacing in tension when multiple cracking is complete should be small e.g. if crack widths in a composite under a 2% tensile strain are to be less than 10 microns, crack spacing should not exceed 0.5 mm. Theoretical principles (4) suggest that crack spacing is minimised by having a high volume fraction of fibre with a high interfacial bond strength and with a large specific surface. Economically the high volume fraction is unattractive, so work has concentrated upon establishing an understanding of the complex bonding mechanism between polypropylene fibres and cement in order to optimise film properties to yield rapid stress transfer from fibre to matrix. To overcome the Poisson contraction of the fibres which debonds the fibre/matrix interface, mechanical interaction between fibre and matrix is encouraged by using fine fibres of high specific surface area possessing a non-uniform thickness distribution. The fibre/matrix misfit encountered as the fibres are pulled through the matrix may be further supplemented by micron-size voiding within the fibres which is subsequently penetrated by cement hydration products. Crack spacings of less than 1mm with consequent very fine crack widths can be achieved at reasonable fibre volumes.

Impact Resistance

One method for measuring the toughness of fibre-reinforced cement sheet materials which fail following multiple cracking of the matrix involves the determination of the area under the tensile stress-strain curve (i.e. the energy absorbed by the composite) and relating this to unit volume of the composite (7). The energy absorbed increases with increasing fibre volume fractions, but considerable improvement in impact resistance can be achieved at economic fibre volumes e.g. the toughness measured in this manner for a polypropylene-reinforced composite containing 5% by volume of aligned fibres is approximately 500 kJ/m^3 compared to 5 kJ/m^3 for asbestos-cement.

Durability

A durability programme has been under way for over 2 years, with cracked and uncracked specimens under two exposure conditions - natural outdoor and indoor air curing. The conclusion so far is that neither condition is detrimental to

the composite. An accelerated test is currently being developed to compare the effectiveness of different anti-oxidants on film performance.

POLYPROPYLENE-REINFORCED CEMENT SHEETING

Strength Performance Requirements

A sheeting material used as a roofing or cladding element will have to sustain the following loads in service, in addition to its own self-weight.

(i) Snow loading (if the possibility of snow exists) which may be long-term in nature and which is uniformly distributed over the sheet surface. In the UK the snow loading requirement is 0.75 kN/m^2 (8). In Western Europe snow loads up to 2 kN/m^2 may have to be sustained.

(ii) Wind loading, short-term and uniformly distributed. Pressure/suction values depend upon a number of factors e.g. location, geometry of structure, but can be $2\text{-}3 \text{ kN/m}^2$ locally on sheets.

(iii) Loading due to foot traffic i.e. concentrated loads arising principally during erection. In UK practice the concentrated load requirement is generally taken as 0.9 kN (8).

In existing and proposed standards for testing fibre-reinforced sheeting elements, uniformly distributed loading is simulated by either a single line load at midspan or two line loads at quarter span positions. Concentrated loading is simulated by loading through square rigid plates. Sizes specified vary between 100mm square and 300 mm square.

The quasi-ductile behaviour of polypropylene reinforced cement compared to brittle asbestos-cement, for which existing standards are written, requires a fresh approach to the determination of allowable loads that sheeting may sustain. For an asbestos-cement sheet with an essentially linear load-deflection relationship to failure and which does not become unserviceable due to excessive deflections or major cracking prior to failure, then it is sufficient simply to provide an adequate factor of safety against collapse. For a quasi-ductile cement composite, serviceability criteria become important and the loads that can be safely sustained may be based on either the load at which significant cracking occurs or the load at which a particular critical deflection is reached, rather than on the collapse or maximum load (although an adequate factor of safety relating to the maximum load will still be required). It would seem reasonable and in line with a probabilistic limit state design approach that allowable loads based on serviceability criteria should be determined using a lower factor of safety than those based on a collapse condition. The British Standard BS 5427 (8) has been developed along these lines to cover all types of sheeting material, but does not appear to have been widely adopted in the sheeting industry. One of the first countries to develop a standard appropriate to quasi-ductile cement sheeting was Denmark (9). The Standard recognises that it is now important to distinguish between a failure or maximum load (since it can prove impossible to break polypropylene-reinforced sheets) and a load at departure from linearity. These loads are defined as shown in Figure 5. However, the standard makes no recommendation on the manner in which design loads should relate to these loads obtained from standard tests.

It is also worth noting that the Standard defines acceptance tests to simulate impact loading caused by a person falling onto sheeting (9).

The difficult problem of assessing durability of new cement composites reinforced by a variety of fibres other than asbestos is under active consideration by international Standards committee.

Tests on Polypropylene-reinforced Cement and Asbestos-cement Corrugated Sheets

Comparative tests on full-size polypropylene-reinforced cement and asbestos-cement sheets have been carried out. The polypropylene reinforced cement sheets

were manufactured by hand as flat sheets and pressed into corrugated form on a mould made from an asbestos-cement sheet of standard profile. Thus both sheet types tested had similar profiles and similar section properties. The polypropylene reinforcement was provided as, approximately, a 5% volume fraction longitudinally (i.e. parallel to the corrugations) and 3% transversely. Sheets were about one metre wide and were tested under two line loads, positioned at quarter span, over a span of 1.38 m, the recommended maximum span for the asbestos-cement sheet.

The load-deflection curves for the two sheet types are shown in Figure 6, together with the general profile shape. The second moment of area of the section of the polypropylene-reinforced sheet was about 10% higher than that of the asbestos-cement sheet. In Figure 6, the loading has been expressed as an equivalent uniformly distributed load per unit area of sheet (between supports). It proved impossible to break the polypropylene-reinforced sheet and loading was stopped when deflection increased rapidly as attempts to apply further load were made. Figure 7 shows the sheet under the maximum equivalent load of 6.1 kN/m². The load at the limit of proportionality determined according to the Danish Standard procedure (Figure 5) was 3.5 kN/m², at a deflection of 3mm or span/450.

The asbestos-cement sheet failed suddenly and broke into two sections at an equivalent load of 5.5 kN/m² when the deflection was 7mm or span/200.

The test to failure on the polypropylene-reinforced cement sheet under the two line loads was followed by a concentrated load test. The sheet easily sustained a load of 1.5 kN applied over a 125 mm square plate on an edge corrugation. The final maximum residual deflection after all tests were complete was 10 mm or span/140.

Behaviour of Polypropylene-reinforced Cement Sheeting Under Long-term Loads

There is no existing requirement in cement sheeting standards for testing under long-term loads, partly because with asbestos-cement, increase of deflection with time has been found, in practice, not to be a problem. Similarly, for polypropylene-reinforced sheeting in the uncracked condition, creep effects under long-term loads are unlikely to be critical. In a cracked sheet, however, significant fibre stresses exist and the creep behaviour of the polymer will cause increased long-term deflections.

Polypropylene-reinforced sheets of two corrugations width and of similar profile to that discussed above have been loaded over a span of 1.38 m under different uniformly distributed loads for a period of over two years. Under a load of 0.75 kN/m² (the UK design snow load), deflections (at 20°C) have not exceeded 4 mm or span/350. The creep of polypropylene under snow at 0°C will, of course, be less than at 20°C.

CONCLUSIONS

A cement composite reinforced by continuous opened networks of fibrillated polypropylene film is an economic alternative to the use of asbestos-cement as a roofing or cladding element. Corrugated sheets of similar profile and section to standard asbestos-cement sheets can sustain the loads required by UK and international Standard specifications and remain serviceable. The impact performance of the sheeting is a considerable improvement over that of asbestos-cement.

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FIGURE 1. Continuous Fibrillated Polypropylene Network.

FIGURE 2. Typical Tensile Stress-strain Curve for Polypropylene-reinforced Composite Containing 7% by Volume of Opened Film Networks.

FIGURE 3. Influence of Fibre Elastic Modulus (E_f) on Tensile Stress-strain Curve (Fibre Volume Fraction 10%).

FIGURE 4. Influence of Fibre Elastic Modulus (E_f) on Load-deflection Curve (Fibre Volume Fraction 11.5%).

FIGURE 5. Load-deflection Curve for Corrugated Sheet. Definition of Loads according to Danish Standard Procedure (9).

FIGURE 6. Load-deflection Curves for Corrugated Sheets.

FIGURE 7. Polypropylene-reinforced Cement Sheet under Equivalent Uniformly Distributed Load of 6.1 kN/m^2 .